

25 **Key words:** quartz; Meyer-Neldel rule; electron spin resonance; $[\text{AlO}_4/\text{h}^+]^0$, $[\text{TiO}_4/\text{M}^+]^0$

26

27 **1. Introduction**

28 Signals from $[\text{AlO}_4/\text{h}^+]^0$ and $[\text{TiO}_4/\text{M}^+]^0$ paramagnetic centres are generally used to date
29 sedimentary quartz by electron spin resonance (ESR) because of their easy identification and
30 quantification, as well as their response to irradiation (Toyoda and Ikeya, 1991a; Rink et al., 2007;
31 Tissoux et al., 2008). Another prerequisite for accurate dating is the use of a thermally stable signal.
32 The two defects are considered to fulfil this requirement at ambient temperature (Toyoda and
33 Ikeya, 1991; Duval et al., 2015 etc.). But, although a comprehensive understanding of the thermal
34 decay kinetics of these defects is of outmost importance not only for dating, but also for
35 thermochronometry (Grün et al., 1999; King et al., 2019), the majority of studies carried so far
36 circumvented the time-consuming determination of laboratory kinetics by adherence to standard
37 literature values, or performed investigations only for a single laboratory given dose, under the
38 assumption that the decay parameters do not depend on the given dose (see e.g. Richter et al, 2020
39 an references therein).

40 For higher doses, a higher density of defects clearly exists, and very recent studies on irradiated
41 ionic solids such as Al_2O_3 , MgO and MgF_2 showed that the defect recombination kinetics is not
42 characterised uniquely by the activation energy with a constant pre-exponent, but instead these
43 parameters depend on the radiation dose (Kotomin et al., 2018; Popov et al., 2018; Baubekova, G.,
44 2020). No studies have so far investigated such a possible effect in quartz.

45 The wide band gap makes quartz an excellent insulator. However, the existence of cations allows
46 the ionic conductivity to take place as a response to electromagnetic and/or thermal excitation. It
47 is generally accepted that the mobility of the ions in hexagonal quartz is mostly taking place

48 through the open c-channel (Martin et al., 1983; Martini et al., 1995; Campone et al., 1995).
49 Aluminium centres in quartz are known to be compensated by monovalent cations M^+ (where M^+
50 is usually H^+ or alkali ions such as Li^+ or Na^+) (Weil, 1975). Under gamma irradiation, $[AlO_4/M^+]^0$
51 interacts with holes, releasing the cation (M^+) and producing $[AlO_4/h^+]^0$ centres (Halliburton,
52 1981). At the same time, $[TiO_4/M^+]^0$ is formed after an electron is trapped by a substitutional
53 titanium ion, forming $[TiO_4]^-$ centre, that also traps a cation acquiring a paramagnetic stable state
54 (Woda and Wagner, 2007). Consequently, the formation of $[AlO_4/h^+]^0$ and $[TiO_4/M^+]^0$ by gamma
55 irradiation occurs by releasing and trapping, respectively, of a cation. The reverse mechanism is
56 known to occur on heating. It was suggested that by heating at around 325 °C, the release of cations
57 from an unidentified defect (denoted as $[XO_4/M^+]^0$) and their trapping at uncompensated Al sites
58 is resulting in the emission of thermoluminescence at this temperature (Itoh, 2002).

59 In this study, we examine the dependence of thermal kinetic parameters as function of the
60 previously given dose for $[AlO_4/h^+]^0$ and $[TiO_4/M^+]^0$, showing that these parameters obey the
61 Meyer-Neldel rule, or in other words during thermal activation the pre-exponential factor depends
62 exponentially on the activation energy in respect of the given dose. Furthermore, our results
63 support the hypothesis of the ionic exchange between $[AlO_4/M^+]^0$ and a second defect, which we
64 hereby assign to $[TiO_4/M^+]^0$, extending thus the previous interpretive studies (Itoh et al., 2002,
65 Williams and Spooner, 2018).

66

67 2. Materials and methods

68 Sedimentary quartz of size between 63 and 90 μm extracted from Holocene soil at loess-palaeosol
69 sequence in Enders, Nebraska, Great Plains (USA), was used. The treatment and extraction
70 procedures were presented in detail in Tecşa et al., 2020. ESR investigations were carried out using

71 X band Bruker EMX plus spectrometer. Room temperature irradiations were performed at Centre
72 for Nuclear Technologies, Technical University of Denmark (DTU NUTECH) using a calibrated
73 ^{60}Co -60 gamma cell, with a dose rate of about 2 Gy/s. The defects effective concentration was
74 quantified by measuring the peak-to-peak amplitude (App) of their ESR signals (Toyoda, 2015).
75 The ESR linewidth was verified to have no-significant variation with dose which makes the ESR-
76 App variation equivalent to the effective concentration variation (Chesnut, 1977). The $[\text{AlO}_4/\text{h}^+]^0$
77 variation is then considered as the similar as that of the difference between the top of the first
78 hyperfine line of the electronic transition due to g_2 and the bottom of the sixth hyperfine line of
79 the electronic transition due to g_3 , whereas that of $[\text{TiO}_4/\text{M}^+]^0$, where M^+ is mainly $^7\text{Li}^+$, was taken
80 as the difference between the top of the electronic transition corresponding to g_1 and the bottom of
81 the electronic transition corresponding to g_3 , knowing that both centres possess an anisotropic g -
82 tensor (see Toyoda et al., 2015). The pulse annealing experiment is characterized by a linear
83 dependence between temperature and time. The temporal variation of temperature can be written
84 as: $T = T_0 + Qt$, where T_0 is the room temperature ($\sim 294\text{K}$), and Q is the heating rate, that can be
85 expressed as $Q = q/t_a$ where t_a is the annealing duration equal to 600s, and q is the temperature
86 increment from pulse to pulse, in our case equal to 50K.

88 3. Results and discussions

89 3.1. Investigated signals

90 **Figure 1** shows the ESR spectra of $[\text{AlO}_4/\text{h}^+]^0$ and $[\text{TiO}_4/\text{M}^+]^0$ centres recorded at 90 K for samples
91 irradiated with gamma doses of 94 Gy as well as 9.4 kGy. It can be noted that the signal of
92 $[\text{TiO}_4/\text{M}^+]^0$ we are quantifying herein corresponds mainly to $[\text{TiO}_4/\text{Li}^+]^0$ because of the observable
93 four hyperfine transitions at the central transition, corresponding to the electronic spin interaction

94 with the 3/2 nuclear spin of ${}^7\text{Li}^+$ (**figure 1a**). However, the last transition towards high magnetic
 95 field is known to be overlapped by that of $[\text{TiO}_4/\text{H}^+]^0$ (Tissoux et al., 2008, Toyoda et al., 2015,
 96 Duval et al., 2017). In the following we are considering that the variation of $[\text{TiO}_4/\text{M}^+]^0$ is mainly
 97 that of $[\text{TiO}_4/\text{Li}^+]^0$.

98

99 **Figure 1:** ESR spectra of $[\text{AlO}_4/\text{h}^+]^0$ and $[\text{TiO}_4/\text{M}^+]^0$ recorded at 90K, with 2mW of microwave
 100 power and 9417 MHz of frequency before annealing (a) and after 10 minutes annealing at 300°C
 101 (b).

102

103 3.2. Thermal decay for different doses

104 **Figure 2** exhibits the dose response curves for $[\text{AlO}_4/\text{h}^+]^0$ and $[\text{TiO}_4/\text{M}^+]^0$ before and after
 105 annealing pulses. For the unheated sample, the $[\text{AlO}_4/\text{h}^+]^0$ dose response is growing with dose until
 106 close to saturation, while the $[\text{TiO}_4/\text{M}^+]^0$ signals exhibit a growth with dose, followed by a

107 pronounced decrease after a certain threshold value (around 10kGy here). The $[\text{AlO}_4/\text{h}^+]^0$ signal
 108 variation with dose is fitted by the model recently proposed by Benzid and Timar-Gabor (2020)
 109 for annealing treatments at a temperature up to 300°C (**figure 2a**). The variation of $[\text{TiO}_4/\text{M}^+]^0$
 110 signal was fitted following the model presented by Woda and Wagner, 2007 up to full annealing
 111 around 350°C (**figure 2.b**).

112

113 **Figure 2:** Evolution of the effective concentration of (a) $[\text{AlO}_4/\text{h}^+]^0$ and (b) $[\text{TiO}_4/\text{M}^+]^0$ as function
 114 of dose after 10 minutes annealing at various temperatures (T_a). Please note the logarithmic scale.

115

116 The decay rate of the signal as function of temperature in the pulse annealing procedure,
 117 considering 1st and 2nd order kinetics can be written as:

$$118 \quad R_H^{1st} = \frac{dN_H(t)}{dt} = -\lambda(T)N_H \quad (1.i)$$

119 and

$$120 \quad R_H^{2nd} = \frac{dN_H(t)}{dt} = -\lambda'(T)N_H^2 = -\lambda(T)\frac{N_H^2}{(N_D - N_0)} \quad (1.ii)$$

121 where $\lambda(T) = \lambda_0 e^{-\left(\frac{E}{K_B T}\right)}$ is the Arrhenius law, λ_0 (Hz) is the frequency factor, E (eV) is the
 122 activation energy, K_B ($8.615 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ eV} \cdot \text{K}^{-1}$) is the Boltzmann constant, $(N_D - N_0)$ is the initial

123 effective concentration in respect of the accumulated gamma dose and $\lambda'(T) = \frac{\lambda(T)}{(N_D - N_0)}$. The
 124 subscript D and H indicates that the parameter is taken in the respect of dose and of temperature
 125 for fixed gamma dose, respectively.

126 Equations (1.i) and (1.ii) can be solved by replacing the time variation (dt) with the temperature
 127 variation (dT) via the heating rate ($Q = dT/dt$ (see section 2)) and integrating from $(N_D - N_0)$ to
 128 N_H and from T_0 to T . The exact solution involves the exponential integral function. However, by
 129 asymptotically approximating the function in second order (Bleistein and Handelsman, 1986), one
 130 obtains for first and second order kinetics effective concentration variation (see Appendix) as:

$$131 \quad N_H^{1st} = (N_D - N_0)e^{-\frac{\lambda_0 K_B}{Q E} \left(T^2 e^{-\left(\frac{E}{K_B T}\right)} - T_0^2 e^{-\left(\frac{E}{K_B T_0}\right)} \right)} \quad (2.i)$$

132 and

$$133 \quad N_H^{2nd} = (N_D - N_0) \left(1 + \frac{\lambda_0 K_B}{Q E} \left(T^2 e^{-\left(\frac{E}{K_B T}\right)} - T_0^2 e^{-\left(\frac{E}{K_B T_0}\right)} \right) \right)^{-1} \quad (2.ii)$$

134 **Figure 3** presents the evolution of the effective concentration of $[AlO_4/h^+]^0$ and $[TiO_4/M^+]^0$ after
 135 accumulating various gamma doses as function of annealing temperature. One can observe that
 136 the effective concentration of both defects remains constant up to annealing temperatures of about
 137 200°C to 250°C. Beyond this temperature range, the concentrations decrease with temperature and
 138 the signals eventually disappear around 350°C and 450°C for $[TiO_4/M^+]^0$ and $[AlO_4/h^+]^0$,
 139 respectively.

140 The datasets in figures inset in 3.a and 3.b have been fitted by equations (2.i) and (2.ii). It was
 141 observed that 2nd order kinetics characterises better the decay, as previously reported by others
 142 (Toyoda and Ikeya, 1991b). The use of both equations gives similar kinetic parameters (E and λ_0).

143 In the following we consider the 2nd order kinetic model ($N_H^{2nd} \equiv N_H$).

144 By examining **figure 3.a** and **3.b**, one can see that high dose signals drop faster than low dose
 145 signals on heating, inferring that the kinetic parameters are dose dependent. As such, one expects
 146 the temperature where the defect concentration ($R_H(T)$) is minimal to be dose dependent too. For
 147 visualisation, we show the absolute variation with temperature ($|R_H(T)|$) in the figures 3.c and
 148 3.d. The variation with temperature (eq.1.ii) gives dose-dependent peaks as function of given dose
 149 at about 280°C to 440°C for $[AlO_4/h^+]^0$ and at about 260°C to 370°C for $[TiO_4/M^+]^0$.

150

151 **Figure 3:** 2nd order kinetic evolution as function of annealing temperature of the effective
 152 concentration of (a) $[AlO_4/h^+]^0$ and (b) $[TiO_4/M^+]^0$ after accumulating various doses (data was
 153 fitted by equation 2.ii. Figures insets in a) and b) show this evolution after accumulating 9.4 kGy
 154 fitted by 1st and 2nd order kinetic according to equations 2.i and 2.ii. Panels c) and d) show the rate
 155 variation of the effective concentrations (eq. 1.ii) for various accumulated gamma doses using the
 156 kinetic parameters given by the fitting in a) and b).

157 **Figure 4** represents dose-dependency of the kinetic parameters (E and λ_0) along the investigated
 158 dose scale beside the ESR amplitudes.

159

160 **Figure 4:** Dose dependency of the datasets fitting parameters in the figure 3; the amplitudes a) of
 161 $[AlO_4/h^+]^0$ and b) of $[TiO_4/M^+]^0$, and of the activation energy and the frequency factor c) of
 162 $[AlO_4/h^+]^0$ and d) of $[TiO_4/M^+]^0$.

163

164 As the thermal decay was not found to follow simple first order kinetics, lifetimes cannot be
 165 computed, strictly speaking (Prokein and Wagner, 1994). However, as an approximation, by using
 166 the values of the activation energy and the frequency factors for $[TiO_4/M^+]^0$ and $[AlO_4/h^+]^0$ and
 167 their change with dose (**figure 4 c and d**) lifetimes, ($\tau = 1/\lambda$) at an estimated average
 168 temperature of 10 °C range from 10^{10} years for doses about 100 Gy to only a couple of years for
 169 doses in the kGy range. A recent study on sedimentary quartz extracted from Chinese loess
 170 (Tsukamoto et al., 2018) suggested that $[TiO_4/M^+]^0$ could be less stable than previously believed.

171 Moreover, the same study presented a concerning discrepancy between the natural and the
172 laboratory generated dose response curves. By investigating quartz samples from Luochuan loess
173 palaeosol sequence where age control is available based on the well-known stratigraphy, signals
174 for both $[AlO_4/h^+]^0$ and $[TiO_4/M^+]^0$ centres recorded for natural samples older than about 300-600
175 ka (corresponding to doses in the 1-2 kGy range) were recorded in field saturation, in other words
176 no longer increasing with age (and hence dose). This indicates that a steady state has been reached.
177 On the other hand, laboratory signals generated by the same doses, however given in a time orders
178 of magnitude shorter than in nature and measured immediately after irradiation displayed no such
179 signs of early saturation. Moreover, in the above mentioned study, the application of a preheat
180 treatment before the measurement of the laboratory dose response curve was shown to change not
181 only the amplitude of the signals, but also the saturation characteristics (D_0 value), or in other
182 words the shape of the dose response curve. This suggests that thermal treatments might have
183 different effects on signals recorded after laboratory irradiations at higher doses, than for low
184 doses.

185 Our results clearly indicate that both $[AlO_4/h^+]^0$ as well as $[TiO_4/M^+]^0$ defects are less thermally
186 stable above 1-2 kGy than below this dose range. This is in perfect agreement with the observations
187 of [Tsukamoto et al., 2018](#) on natural dose response curves constructed on quartz from Chinese
188 loess, described above.

189 By further analysing the values obtained for the frequency factor and activation energy we show
190 (**figure 5**) a very important feature of these defects under thermal activation, namely the fact that
191 the frequency factor depends exponentially on the activation energy, or in other words that the
192 kinetic parameters satisfy the Meyer–Neldel rule.

193

194 **Figure 5.** Correlation of the activation energies and the preexponents obtained for different doses
 195 for $[\text{AlO}_4/\text{h}^+]^0$ (a) and $[\text{TiO}_4/\text{M}^+]^0$ (b). A standard person correlation coefficient of 0.989 and
 196 0.996, respectively was obtained. Isokinetic energies found to be 0.058 eV and 0.068 eV
 197 corresponding to temperatures of about and 411 °C and 522 °C, respectively.

198

199 The variation of the activation energy as function of the frequency factor as can be written from
 200 equation 2.ii as:

$$201 \quad E = (K_B T) \ln \left(R_H \frac{N_D - N_0}{N_H^2} \right) + (K_B T) \ln(\lambda_0) \quad (3)$$

202 This equation has been used the fit the dataset in the figure 5.

203 The Meyer–Neldel rule is well known in different processes although the basis of this empirical
 204 rule is not fully understood yet. However, it is known to accompany the rise of macroscopic

205 disordering in materials under irradiation which is not necessarily accompanied by amorphization
206 (Kotomin, 2018; Baubekova et al., 2020).

207

208 3.3. Correlation between $[AlO_4/h^+]^0$ and $[TiO_4/M^+]^0$

209 Benzid and Timar-Gabor, 2020 presented a phenomenological model for the formation of
210 $[AlO_4/h^+]^0$, based on the dissociation of $[AlO_4/M^+]^0$ that allowed explaining the shape (sum of two
211 saturating exponential functions) of the empirical dose response curve, by considering the different
212 nature of the cation denoted by M^+ (hydrogen or alkali). Regardless to cation nature, the formation
213 of $[AlO_4/h^+]^0$ can be simplified as:

215 For the $[TiO_4/M^+]^0$ centre, Woda and Wagner (2007) proposed the following mechanisms to occur
216 under gamma irradiation; (i) irradiation-induced formation up to certain dose by trapping one
217 electron followed by (ii) irradiation-induced annihilation by trapping a second electron:

219 According to the mechanisms (a) and (b.i), the growth of $[AlO_4/h^+]^0$ and $[TiO_4/M^+]^0$, occurs by
220 releasing and trapping cations, respectively. Thus, there is a reasonable possibility that the cations
221 released from $[AlO_4/M^+]^0$ are being trapped by $[TiO_4/M^+]^0$. Also, it is likely that defect annealing
222 is the reverse of its formation.

223 If one considers that the formation mechanism of both defects under gamma irradiation follows
224 first order kinetics, hence the production rates is proportional to the defect concentration, the ratio
225 of the production rates of the two defects, defined as R_D^{Al-h}/R_D^{Ti-M} can be expressed as:

$$226 \frac{R_D^{Al-h}}{R_D^{Ti-M}} = \frac{\Gamma^{Al-h} (N_D^{Al-h} - N_0^{Al-h})}{\Gamma^{Ti-M} (N_D^{Ti-M} - N_0^{Ti-M})} \quad (4)$$

227 Where $\Gamma^{\text{Al-h}}$ and $\Gamma^{\text{Ti-M}}$ (Gy^{-1}) are the effective rate constants of mechanisms (a) and (b.i),
 228 respectively; $N_{\text{D}}^{\text{Al-h}}$ and $N_{\text{D}}^{\text{Ti-M}}$ (a.u) are the effective concentration, taken here conventionally as
 229 the ESR-App; $N_0^{\text{Al-h}}$ and $N_0^{\text{Ti-M}}$ (a.u) are the initial concentrations. The subscript D indicates that
 230 the parameter is taken in the respect of the dose for a fixed temperature. Equation 4 can be
 231 rearranged as:

$$232 \quad N_{\text{D}}^{\text{Al-h}} = N_0^{\text{Al-h}} + B \left(N_{\text{D}}^{\text{Ti-M}} - N_0^{\text{Ti-M}} \right) \text{ where } B = \frac{R_{\text{D}}^{\text{Al-h}} \Gamma^{\text{Ti-M}}}{R_{\text{D}}^{\text{Ti-M}} \Gamma^{\text{Al-h}}} \quad (5)$$

233 **Figure 6** represents the evolution of the effective concentration of $[\text{AlO}_4/\text{h}^+]^0$ as function of that
 234 of $[\text{TiO}_4/\text{M}^+]^0$ in respect of accumulated dose, up to 10 kGy, after 10 minutes annealing at various
 235 temperatures.

236
 237 **Figure 6:** Evolution of the effective concentration of $[\text{AlO}_4/\text{h}^+]^0$ as function of that of $[\text{TiO}_4/\text{M}^+]^0$
 238 in the respect of gamma dose, up to 10 kGy and above 10 kGy (inset), for 10 minutes annealing at
 239 various temperatures. The dashed red line indicates to the correlation line (equation 5).

240 One can see that the paramagnetic defects show a temperature-independent correlation. Equation
 241 5 was used to fit the dataset. The temperature-independent proportionality constant B is found to
 242 be ~ 5.2 . The weak value of $N_0^{\text{Ti-M}}$ (~ 0.1) makes the intercept about the initial concentration of
 243 $[\text{AlO}_4/\text{h}^+]^0$ (~ 1.6 a.u). This high relatively initial concentration is due to the significant values of
 244 the residual of this defect (see further details in [Timar-Gabor et al., 2020](#)). Above 10kGy, after
 245 $[\text{TiO}_4/\text{M}^+]^0$ experienced the radiation bleaching, the correlation does not longer hold. However,
 246 the decrease of $[\text{TiO}_4/\text{M}^+]^0$ by annealing correlates with the that of $[\text{AlO}_4/\text{h}^+]^0$ (**Figure 6** inset).
 247 By calculating the rate ratio ($R_{\text{H}}^{\text{Al-h}}/R_{\text{H}}^{\text{Ti-M}}$) of trapping/releasing cations by $[\text{AlO}_4/\text{h}^+]^0$ /
 248 $[\text{TiO}_4/\text{M}^+]^0$, one can write:

$$249 \quad \Delta E = E^{\text{Ti-M}} - E^{\text{Al-h}} = -(K_{\text{B}}T) \ln \left(\frac{R_{\text{H}}^{\text{Ti-M}} (N_{\text{H}}^{\text{Al-h}})^2 (N_{\text{D}}^{\text{Ti-M}} - N_0^{\text{Ti-M}})}{R_{\text{H}}^{\text{Al-h}} (N_{\text{H}}^{\text{Ti-M}})^2 (N_{\text{D}}^{\text{Al-h}} - N_0^{\text{Al-h}})} \right) + (K_{\text{B}}T) \ln \left(\frac{\lambda_0^{\text{Ti-M}}}{\lambda_0^{\text{Al-h}}} \right) \quad (6)$$

250 This is represented in **figure 7**.

251

252 **Figure 7:** Evolution of the cation activation energies difference during the releasing/trapping
 253 process from $[\text{TiO}_4/\text{M}^+]^0$ to $[\text{AlO}_4/\text{h}^+]^0$. The inset represents a possible schematic of the energy
 254 diagram.

255 From the fitting of the datasets by equation (6) in **figure 7** and by equation (5) in **figure 6** one can
 256 get the following proportionalities between the effective concentrations of the two defects under
 257 both gamma irradiation and thermal pulse annealing processes:

$$258 \frac{R_H^{\text{Ti-M}}(N_H^{\text{Al-h}})^2(N_D^{\text{Ti-M}}-N_0^{\text{Ti-M}})}{R_H^{\text{Al-h}}(N_H^{\text{Ti-M}})^2(N_D^{\text{Al-h}}-N_0^{\text{Al-h}})} = \frac{R_D^{\text{Al-h}}\Gamma^{\text{Ti-M}}}{R_D^{\text{Ti-M}}\Gamma^{\text{Al-h}}} = \frac{(N_D^{\text{Al-h}}-N_0^{\text{Al-h}})}{(N_D^{\text{Ti-M}}-N_0^{\text{Ti-M}})} = \frac{\lambda_0^{\text{Ti-M}}}{\lambda_0^{\text{Al-h}}} e^{\left(\frac{\Delta E}{k_B T}\right)} = B \cong 5.2 \quad (7)$$

259 According to equation 6 used to fit the data presented in **figure 7** the compensation energy for
 260 cations to migrate from $[\text{TiO}_4/\text{M}^+]^0$ to $[\text{AlO}_4/\text{h}^+]^0$ and vice-versa was found to be 51.3 ± 4 meV. The
 261 corresponding Meyer–Neldel temperature is found to be about 325°C in perfect match with the
 262 thermoluminescence band previously proposed by [Itoh et al., 2002](#) to originate from the migration
 263 of M^+ to an Al site from a then unidentified defect.

264

265 4. Summary

266 Due to neutrality principle, substitutional Al in quartz is compensated by monovalent cations
 267 (hydrogen and/or alkali ions) forming $[\text{AlO}_4/\text{M}^+]^0$ centres. Under gamma irradiation, the cations
 268 are replaced by holes producing paramagnetic $[\text{AlO}_4/\text{h}^+]^0$. At the same time, the diamagnetic
 269 $[\text{TiO}_4]^-$ traps the cations forming the paramagnetic $[\text{TiO}_4/\text{M}^+]^0$. Under thermal excitation, the
 270 reverse process occurs, namely the cations displace from $[\text{TiO}_4/\text{M}^+]^0$ to $[\text{AlO}_4/\text{h}^+]^0$, converting
 271 them to their diamagnetic precursors, $[\text{TiO}_4]^-$ and $[\text{AlO}_4/\text{M}^+]$, respectively. This process is
 272 governed by the activation energies of cations and the effective lattice vibration frequencies of the
 273 medium. These parameters were found to be dose dependent. This find clearly calls for future
 274 investigations when it comes to using electron spin resonance for dating in the high dose range or
 275 for thermochronometry applications. By analysing samples exposed to different radiation doses,
 276 the process was found to obey the Meyer-Neldel rule. A compensation energy of 51.3 ± 4 meV was
 277 estimated, corresponding to a temperature about 325°C . We thus support the assignment of the

278 thermoluminescence band at 325°C to the recombination of the thermally displaced cation, here
279 mainly assigned as Li⁺ from [TiO₄/M⁺]⁰ to [AlO₄/h⁺]⁰.

280

281 **Supplementary Material**

282 Please see supplementary material for derivation of equations (2.i) and (2.ii).

283

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291

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393 Data availability statement for manuscript

394 “The compensation effect (Meyer-Neldel rule) on $[\text{AlO}_4/\text{h}^+]^0$ and $[\text{TiO}_4/\text{M}^+]^0$ paramagnetic
395 centres in irradiated sedimentary quartz”.

396

397 The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon
398 reasonable request.

399

400 Sincerely,

401 Benzid Khalif and Alida Timar-Gabor

402

